

Copper (II) Catalysed Oxidation of Tellurium (IV) by Peroxydisulphate

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The kinetics of the oxidation of tellurium(IV) to tellurium(VI) by peroxydisulphate using copper(II) as the catalyst has been studied. The reaction showed first order dependence to peroxydisulphate zero order dependence to tellurium (IV) and half order dependence to the concentration of copper(II). The energy and the entropy of activation have been calculated as 32.6 Kcals and 25.3 e.u. respectively. A suitable mechanism has been proposed on the basis of chain mechanistic treatment which involves the intermediate formation of copper(I).

The kinetics of the silver (I) catalysed oxidation of tellurium (IV) by peroxydisulphate has been reported earlier from these laboratories¹. Despite the high redox-potential of the system $S_2O_8^{2-} + 2e = 2SO_4^{2-}$ viz., 2.01 volts² the uncatalysed oxidation of tellurium (IV)

Fig. 1. Plot of Te(IV) concentration versus time. (I) $K_2S_2O_8$ —0.050M, (II) $K_2S_2O_8$ —0.075M, (III) $K_2S_2O_8$ —0.10M and (IV) $K_2S_2O_8$ —0.125M.

is quite slow by this oxidant. However, in presence of copper (II) the reaction is comparatively speeded up. In the present communication, the kinetics of the copper (II) catalysed oxidation of tellurium (IV) by peroxydisulphate in sulphuric acid media has been investigated.

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1. R. K. Shinghal, M. C. Agrawal and S. P. Mushran, *Z. physik. Chem. neue folge* 1968, **62**, 112.

2. W. H. Latimer. *The Oxidation States of Elements and their Potentials in Aqueous Solutions*, Prentice Hall, New York (1952).

EXPERIMENTAL

Aqueous solutions of peroxydisulphate were always prepared fresh by dissolving exact amount of potassium peroxydisulphate (GR, E. Merck) in bidistilled water. Solutions of tellurium (IV) were prepared from potassium tellurite and their strength was checked by usual methods³. Aqueous solution of copper sulphate (AR, BDH) supplied the catalyst copper (II). The reactions were initially studied in an acidic media (0.05M H₂SO₄) and at a constant temperature *viz.*, 45°.

5 ml. aliquot portions of the reaction mixture were transferred at definite intervals of time into titrating vessels containing known amount of potassium permanganate, 2 ml. of 60% sodium phosphate and about 10 ml of sulphuric acid (5M). The presence of sodium phosphate prevents the formation of manganese dioxide. The excess permanganate was titrated against standard oxalic acid which in turn directly gave the amount of tellurium (IV) at a particular time.

RESULTS

Stoichiometry: The reaction vessel containing K₂S₂O₈, 0.05M, K₂TeO₃, 0.0025M in 0.05M H₂SO₄ and 0.001M cupric sulphate was allowed to stand for twenty-four hours in a thermostat at 45°. The amount of persulphate left and tellurium (IV) consumed showed that the reaction may be represented by the following stoichiometric equation:

Tellurium (IV) Dependence: The reaction has been found to be independent of the concentration of the reducing substrate. Fairly agreeable values of zero order rate constants (k_0) with respect to tellurium (IV) have been obtained from the slope of the plot of 'C' against 't' (Fig. 1) which are unaffected by a two fold change in the concentration of tellurium (IV). The results are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Tellurium (IV) Dependence

Initial concentration of K ₂ TeO ₃ , M ^a	$k_0 \times 10^{5b}$ mole min ⁻¹
0.00250	4.02
0.00375	4.02
0.00500	3.99

^a K₂S₂O₈—0.125M, CuSO₄—0.0005M

^b Zero order rate constants with respect to tellurium(IV).

Peroxydisulphate Dependence : The results of the effect of increasing the peroxydisulphate concentration presented in Table 2 show an increasing effect on the zero order rate constants with respect to tellurium (IV). Further, $k_0/[\text{peroxydisulphate}]$ has a fairly constant value showing the first order dependence to peroxydisulphate.

TABLE 2
Peroxydisulphate Dependence

[Peroxydisulphate] M^a	$k_0 \times 10^5$ mole min ⁻¹	$k_0 \times 10^5 /$ [Peroxydisulphate]
0.125	4.02	32
0.100	3.40	34
0.075	2.8	37
0.050	1.94	38

a — K_2TeO_3 —0.0025M, $CuSO_4$ —0.0005M.

Copper (II) Dependence : Copper (II) ion has been found to show quite a prominent catalytic effect on the rate of oxidation of tellurium (IV) by peroxydisulphate. The results of the effect of three different concentrations of the catalyst at various temperatures are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3
Copper (II) Dependence

[Copper(II)] _a M	$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1}$		
	45°	40°	35°
0.0000	10.1	4.86	1.90
0.0005	17.3	7.46	3.29
0.0010	22.9	9.97	4.19
0.0020	34.1	14.9	6.40

a K_2TeO_3 —0.0025M, $K_2S_2O_8$ —0.10M.

Figure 2 shows the plot of $\log k_1$ against $\log [Cu(II)]$ which gives straight lines having slope equal to 0.5. This shows that the reaction is of half order in copper (II).

Influence of several other factors was also studied on the rate of the oxidation. K^+ ion showed an inhibitory effect on the rate of reaction while Ag^+ ion strongly catalysed the oxidation of tellurium (IV) by peroxydisulphate. By the study of the influence of temperature, the magnitudes of energy and entropy of activation have been found out as 32.6 Kcals. and 25.3 cal. deg⁻¹ mole⁻¹ respectively. Deaeration considerably slows down the rate of the reaction.

DISCUSSION

The rate of copper (II) catalysed oxidation of tellurium (IV) by peroxydisulphate has been found to be of first order to peroxydisulphate zero order to tellurium (IV) and half order to copper (II), although the reaction follows a unimolecular rate law at constant concentration of copper (II).

Ben zvi and Allen⁴ have suggested a free radical chain mechanism, involving the oxidation of copper (II) to copper (III) for the interaction of oxalate ion with peroxydisulphate. Woods, Kolthoff and Meehan⁵ have, however, postulated the existence of an intermediate Cu (I), for the copper (II) catalysed oxidation of arsenic (III) by peroxydisulphate.

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log [\text{Cu(II)}]$ versus $\log k_1$ at different temperatures.

For the copper (II) catalysed reaction between tellurium (IV) and peroxydisulphate it appears that the process of oxidation proceeds by a chain mechanism initiated by the decomposition of peroxydisulphate into two sulphate free radicals (Step I). On the basis of the mechanism suggested by Kolthoff *et al.*⁵, the subsequent reactions constituting the chain are proposed, in an air saturated solution, as follows :

4. E. Benzvi and T. L. Allen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 1352.

5. R. Woods, I. M. Kolthoff and E. J. Meehan, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 697.

The stoichiometry of the chain agrees with the experimental results. The chain termination steps are suggested by the following series :

Assuming steady state hypothesis for $[\text{Cu(I)}]$, $[\text{SO}_4^-]$, $[\text{Te(V)}]$, $[\text{HO}_2]$, $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]$ we get a quadratic equation in $[\text{Cu(I)}]$ as follows :

$$\frac{k_5}{k_1} [\text{Cu(I)}]^2 + \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{k_9[\text{Te(IV)}]}{k_7[\text{Cu(I)}]}} \right\} [\text{Cu(I)}] - \frac{k_4}{k_6} [\text{Cu(II)}] = 0 \quad (10)$$

The coefficient of Cu(I) obviously cannot exceed 2, while $k_5[\text{Cu(I)}] \gg k_1$

Accordingly
$$[\text{Cu(I)}] = \frac{k_1 k_4}{k_5 k_6} [\text{Cu(II)}]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (11)$$

and
$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] = \left(\frac{k_1 k_4 k_5}{k_6} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} [\text{Cu(II)}]^{\frac{1}{2}} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \quad (12)$$

According to above derived rate law (12) the rate of the reaction would be proportional to $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$ and $[\text{Cu(II)}]^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and independent of $[\text{Te(IV)}]$. Our experimental results are thus in complete accordance with the mechanism proposed.

The formation of sulphate free radicals has been established by the action of allyl acetate which is an efficient captor for sulphate free radicals without attacking peroxydisulphate. The formation of hydroperoxo-radical (HO_2) during the chain propagation has been reported by earlier workers⁶.

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